

Incredible Indian Women Power

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Abstract

The Indian Women has been making waves over the last two decade. In news, Indian businesswomen have been leaving a mark at various international tournaments. In many ways it is a glorious time for women in India. In recent times there have also been dire claims on the state of violence against women, lack of equal rights in not just work places but also other areas such as sports, politics, arts,culture and overall society have become issues of national concern and rightly so!. However, despite the odds, there have been numerous women that have put India's name on the world map. With resilience and strength women in India have been beacons of hope and inspiration for generations overcoming prejudices, cultural barriers and inequality.

Introduction

The Indian Women has been making waves over the last decade. A landmark judgment by the Delhi High Court ruled that a woman can be a karta, a unique position of leadership in the Family defined by ancient Indian texts that has historically always been held by men. In a debate that stirred the nation, groups of women demanded equal rights to gain access and entry to places of worship. In other news, Indian businesswomen have been leaving a mark at various international tournaments. In many ways it is a glorious time for women in India. With resilience and strength women in India have been beacons of hope and inspiration for generations overcoming prejudices, cultural barriers and inequality.

Recent Times

In recent times there have also been dire claims on the state of violence against women, lack of equal rights in not just work places but also other areas such as sports, politics, arts,culture and overall society have become issues of national concern and rightly so!. However, despite the odds, there have been numerous women that have put India's name on the world map.

From business leaders who are at the helm of affairs at some of India's largest financial, technology and consumer business, to political power houses, sportswomen who have trained with dedication often with little resources or support, women who have authored globally acclaimed books, made music, arts and films that have wowed audiences the world over, climbed Everest, been on space missions, stood up for animal rights, feminism and societal welfare. It is their examples that we can all emulate.Let's look at some of these successful, wonderful women and learn from their experiences to chart our own path to success.

Path to Success

Step Out on the Court with a Clear Goal

Sania Mirza, Saina Nehwal and P.V.Sindhu have witnessed prejudice throughout their career—whether it was critics who wrote them off too soon or even their own extended family who were not too thrilled with their career choices. Saina has, however, come a long way since, and once said, “Once you are satisfied with your goal, it is the real happiness.” Get your head in the game and eye on your target, and you are set to roll! Now Sania Mirza is one of the elite Women’s doublesplayers in the World, Saina Nehwal and P.V.Sindhu are the World Top Five Badminton players. Both secured medals in the Olympics for India and came with flying colors. Hima Das, nicknamed the “Dhing Express”, is an Indian sprint runner from the state of Assam. She holds the current Indian national record in 400 metres with a timing of 50.79 s that she clocked at the 2018 Asian Games in Jakarta Indonesia. She is the first Indian athlete to win a gold medal in a track event at the IAAF World U20 Championships. Her parents are basically farmers.

Channel Your Inner

The five times world boxing champion Mary Kom once shared her story of determination saying, “people used to say that boxing is for men and not for women and I thought I will show them some day. I promised myself and I proved myself.” Hailing from a humble background, Mary Kom had to overcome insurmountable odds right from limited financial backing to undue societal and cultural pressures. Mary Kom, mother of two kids achieved and got Olympic medal for India. True grit, single-minded determination and relentless perseverance are perhaps the biggest key to her successes. Dipa Karmakar is an Indian artistic gymnast, first gained attention when she won a bronze medal at the 2014 Commonwealth Games in Glasgow becoming the first Indian female gymnast to do so in the history of the Games. She also won a bronze medal at the Asian Gymnastics Championships and finished fifth at the 2015 World Artistic Gymnastics Championships, both firsts for her country. Karmakar represented India at the 2016 Summer Olympics in Rio de Janeiro, becoming the first Indian female gymnast ever to compete in the Olympics, and the first Indian gymnast to do so in 52 years. Mithali Dorai Raj is an Indian cricketer and the captain of the Indian women’s cricket team in Tests and ODI Often regarded as one of the greatest batswomen to have ever played the game, she is the highest run-scorer in women’s international cricket and the only female cricketer to surpass the 6,000 run mark in WODIs.

Winning Combination

The corporate landscape in India is dotted with umber-successful women. Kiran Mazumdar Shaw of Biocon, Arundhati Bhattacharya of State Bank of India, Chandra Kochar of ICICI Bank, Naina Lal Kidwai of HSBC Bank are all shining examples of women who have broken through the infamous glass ceiling, rallied faith and confidence among their employees, partners and customers and emerged as leaders who can not only take their organizations to the peak of success but also redefine and shape the industries that we are in. International Monetary Fund (IMF) Managing Director Christine Lagarde appointed Gita Gopinath on Monday as Economic Counsellor and Director of the IMF’s Research Department. Ms. Gopinath currently serves as the John Zwaanstra Professor of International Studies and Economics at Harvard University “Gita is one of the world’s outstanding economists, with impeccable academic credentials, a proven track record of intellectual leadership, and extensive international experience,” Ms. Lagarde said. They seem to have cracked the code to achieving the elusive work-life balance, managing careers and homes seemingly effortlessly.

Undeterred Focus

Adopt Indra Nooyi's winning combination of humility and undeterred focus. It, of course, isn't as simple as they make it seem- Indira Nooyi, global chairperson and CEO of PepsiCo, famously acknowledged that women cannot have it all. In an interview where she delved into achieving one's goals she advised: "Just because you are CEO, don't think you have landed. You must continually increase your learning, the way you think, and the way you approach the organization. I have never forgotten that, No matter how fast you grow or far you go in achieving your goals." Staying relevant and ahead of the curve in a rapidly evolving world can only be achieved through a process of continuous improvement. While a single minded focus on the goal is critical, one cannot be weighed down by challenges.

Learn from Deepika Padukone's Poise

The actress, who singularly called out the misogyny of a leading Indian Newspaper on Twitter, also spoke openly about her challenges with depression and how she dealt with it. In advice that holds universally true for women the world over she has been quoted saying, "I feel ups and downs are a part of one's career, and this totally depends on how you take it. You can either be knocked down by the negative things, or you can take it in a positive way and learn from it." True courage, as they say, does not come from the lack of fear in a situation, but in overcoming it. After all, hard work and perseverance will only take you so far, it is ultimately strength of character and spirit that will carry you.

Sky is their Limit

The wonderful execution of PSLV- C 27 with 104 Satellites send to Orbit by India Astro Scientists of ISRO was a World record. This mission was successful coordinated by the Women Scientists. They are Minal Sampath, Anuradha, Ritu Karidhal, Moumita Dutta, Nanthini Harinath, Kriti Faujdar, Valarmathi and Tessy Thomas. ISRO Mars mission success was also by Women ISRO Wing lead by Nandhini Harinath, Seetha Somasundaram and Minal Rohit.

Conclusion

Be good to yourself. As Maya Angelou, American author, poet and civil rights activist, once said, "If I am not good to myself, how can I expect anyone else to be good to me?" In order to earn the respect of others, it is critical to respect yourself and stand up for your rights and beliefs. With no faith in ourselves, we will never be able to inspire faith in others!

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